

**SUBSTANTIVE PHRASES REPRESENTING DISEASE NAMES IN
ENGLISH LANGUAGE****Abdullayev Akhmadjon Khasanovich**Teacher of the Department of foreign languages,
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Abstract: This article deals with such general linguistic problems as the structure of the word, lexical system, phraseological system of the Uzbek and English languages. Nomination of concepts in terms of medicine system of terminology in the form of a substantive word, i.e., in the form of a noun takes place in all three languages. On the whole they have similarities on the ways of lexical substantive nomination in the form of simple noun, affixation derivation, compound word and on semantics derivation.

Key words: terminology, medical terms, affixation derivation, semantics, lexical system, English language, linguistic problems.

The use of terminological and professional vocabulary used by people of the same profession, working in the same field of science and technology, is socially limited. Terms and professionalisms are given in explanatory dictionaries with the mark “special”; sometimes the scope of use of a particular term is indicated: physics, medicine, mathematics, astronomer. etc. Each area of knowledge has its own terminological system.

Terms are words or phrases that name special concepts of any special field of science, technology, or art. Each term is necessarily based on a definition (definition) of the reality it denotes, due to which the terms represent an accurate and at the same time concise description of an object or phenomenon. Each branch of knowledge operates with its own terms, which form the essence of the terminological system of this science (11, p.90).

Medical vocabulary combines special and non-special medical names that function in scientific and other subsystems of the language. The main part of medical vocabulary is medical terminology. Currently, lexicology of the language of science is one of the most actively developed areas of modern linguistics.

The research work analyzed diseases from the point of view of syntactic structure.

The terminology of diseases is very diverse. The term disease can be expressed either as a word or as a complex or simple phrase. Also, the terminology of diseases may include words of Russian, Greek, Latin origin and words that arose from Western European languages.

In the clinic, the concept of disease is most often expressed in two-part words formed using term elements of Greek - Latin origin. For example, cardiopathia (yurak kasalligi).

In annotations of medicinal products in the names of diseases, as a rule, words, phrases and abbreviations of English origin are used.

Several groups stand out. The first group includes diseases expressed by a noun. The second group includes simple phrases consisting of two words. The third group includes complex phrases consisting of three or more words. Let's look at the names of diseases in the annotations from the indications for use from a syntactic point of view:

Names of diseases expressed by them. noun:

Gastritis. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Colitis. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

ARVI. The name of the disease is an abbreviation and is expressed by a noun.

Chlamydia. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Pneumonia. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Flu. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Rhinorrhea. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Trichomonas. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Giardiasis. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Otitis. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Diaper rash. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Burns. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Folliculitis. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Boils. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Conjunctivitis. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Blepharitis. The name of the disease is expressed by the noun.

Diseases expressed in simple phrases:

1. Diabetes mellitus. The phrase is expressed adj. + noun.

Urogenital infection. The phrase is expressed adj. + noun.

Intrauterine infection. The phrase is expressed adj. + noun.

Feverish syndrome. The phrase is expressed adj. + noun.

Traumatic brain injury. The phrase is expressed as a complex adj. + noun.

Neurotic disorders. The phrase is expressed adj. + noun.

Arterial hypotension. The phrase is expressed adj. + noun.

Arterial hypertension. The phrase is expressed adj. + noun.

Infectious wounds. The phrase is expressed adj. + noun.

Purulent wounds. The phrase is expressed adj. + noun.

Gonococcal infection. The phrase is expressed adj. + noun.

2. Meniere's syndrome. The phrase is expressed by a noun. + noun gen.

Migraine prevention. The phrase is expressed by a noun.

Angina attack. The phrase is expressed by a noun.

Skin cracks. The phrase is expressed by a noun.

Gastrointestinal infections. A phrase containing an abbreviation is expressed as a noun.

Prevention of sepsis. The phrase is expressed by a noun.

Names of diseases expressed in complex phrases:

Symptomatic treatment of heartburn. A complex phrase is expressed by adj. + noun.

Cerebrovascular insufficiency. A complex phrase is expressed by a noun.

Digestive insufficiency syndrome. A complex phrase is expressed by a noun.

Prevention of supraventricular tachyarrhythmias. A complex phrase is expressed by a noun + adj.

High blood pressure. A complex phrase is expressed by adj. + adj. + noun

Essential arterial hypertension. A complex phrase is expressed by adj. + noun

Purulent-inflammatory processes of the skin. Complex phrase expressed complex adj. + noun

Purulent ulcer of the cornea. A complex phrase is expressed by adj. + noun

Urinary tract infections. A complex phrase is expressed by a noun. + adj.

Infections of the genital organs. A complex phrase is expressed by a noun. + adj.

Ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke. A complex phrase is expressed by adj. + conjunction and + adj. + noun

Acute and chronic diarrhea. A complex phrase is expressed by adj. + conjunction and + adj. + noun

Diseases of the central nervous system. A complex phrase is expressed by a noun. + adj. + adj. + noun gen

Peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum. A complex phrase is expressed adj. + noun. + noun genus + conjunction and + adj. + noun

Disturbance of the physiological flora of the small and large intestines. A complex phrase is expressed by a noun. + adj. + noun in gender + adj. + conjunction and + adj. + noun in birthplace

Infectious and inflammatory diseases of the oral cavity and pharynx. A complex phrase is expressed by a complex adj. + noun + noun in genus n. + noun in genus n. + conjunction and + noun. in genus.

We can conclude that, firstly, all three groups appear in approximately equal proportions in drug annotations. Secondly, diseases represented by one word are expressed by a noun in the nominative case. Thirdly, diseases represented by simple phrases are expressed either by a noun in the nominative case + an adjective name, or by a noun in the nominative case + a noun in the genitive case. Fourthly, diseases representing complex phrases can contain from three to seven, or even more, words. As a rule, these are nouns in the nominative and genitive cases, adjectives, as well as the conjunction and.

Medical terminology is the language in which doctors of various specialties communicate. It should be clear to the reader and listener regarding the concepts. The most acceptable words for existence in medical terminology should be those that are accepted by most specialists, understandable to everyone and reflect the essence of the phenomenon or subject. The semantic meaning of a particular term in medicine only becomes public knowledge when it is fixed in a precise term that does not allow for different interpretations, is simple, unambiguous (4, p. 24). In any language, vocabulary is the most mobile part of it. Word formation in it occurs spontaneously and the forms of this process are varied, which is an indicator of the degree of development of the language, since words here enter into synonymous relationships and acquire polysemy. A peculiarity of the Latin language is its strict subordination to the basics of medical and pharmaceutical terminology, nominations - the expression in Latin terms of scientific concepts in theoretical and practical disciplines of biomedical and medical content.

For all sciences, including medical science, the statement is true that terminology reflects the result of the cognitive process in a given field of knowledge. The term is a tool of knowledge, since it makes it possible to enrich scientific facts, increase knowledge and transfer it to the next generations of scientists. The endless process of learning the world, the emergence of new and modernization of existing concepts, the discovery and creation of more and more new objects of reality require the language to

provide the community speaking a given language with the necessary number of words for their nomination. The abundance of terms makes it difficult to memorize them, however, “fitted” to some widely known and frequently used word, they quickly enter into everyday speech and then become fixed in the language, since the stereotypic nature of the abbreviation forms makes it possible to easily store them in memory.

Based on this, we can conclude that the terminology used in medical annotations is limitless in terms of its word-formation capabilities. Having no equivalents in other languages, the analyzed terms are borrowed by various languages and become part of the international vocabulary.

But medical terminology in medical annotations is not a positive phenomenon. The oversaturation of annotations with medical and chemical terms leads to the fact that a person without special education is unable to understand the content of the annotation.

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